

Coagulation of Colloidal Titanic Hydroxide.

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The literature on the stability of positively charged hydrosols shows that though much work has been done on hydrosols of oxides of metals (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4434; Samsonow, *Kolloid Z.*, 1911, 8, 96) very little work has been carried out with the hydrosol of titanium oxide. In view of the fact that titanium oxide constitutes an important ingredient of the soil, the nature of whose reaction with different electrolytes at present forms a subject of considerable interest, a hydrosol of titanic oxide was prepared and its coagulation by several electrolytes as affected by ethyl and methyl alcohols, was investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Equi-coagulating concentrations of different electrolytes were determined in the following manner (Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 794): Equal volumes of the sol and the electrolyte were mixed in a dry Jena glass trough which was placed before an incandescent filament carrying a constant current. The times in which the sharp outline of the filament, as viewed through the trough, just disappeared, were noted for comparing the relative coagulating effects. Generally two readings had to be taken to note the exact point of disappearance especially when the time of coagulation was as small as 30 secs. It was found convenient to compare concentrations of electrolytes which produced this 'reference standard' of opalescence in 30 secs. The same colloid was used in each set of comparisons and the same procedure rigorously followed as it is well-known that slight variations, such as shaking or adding small quantities at a time, give totally different coagulating periods. (Cp. Freundlich, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 44, 129).

The colloid was prepared by taking conductivity water in a well washed parchment dialyser and carefully adding Kahlbaum's

chemically pure titanium chloride, drop by drop. After the fumes of hydrochloric acid had disappeared, the solution was dialysed for a fortnight, changing the dialysate every day. The precipitate produced on the first addition of the salt gradually passed into the colloidal state with time, until after a fortnight no precipitate was left at the bottom. At the end of the period, the dialysate did not show a greater turbidity with a solution of silver nitrate than tap water. During the course of any one set of experiments the colloid was tested from time to time with a particular strength of one electrolyte to detect changes in the coagulation time as defined above, resulting from ageing.

Sols A and B are different preparations. Sol C is a sample of sol B kept in a separate bottle and used after three months. The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Concentration of the sol : Titanium in 100 c.c. of the sol in terms of TiO_2 in gm.	Equi-coagulating concentrations in normality.					
	KCl	KBr	KNO_3	K_2SO_4	$\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$
0.43 (Sol A)	0.5	0.75	0.6	0.016	0.0013	0.00057
0.23 (Sol B)	0.016	—	0.017	0.0019	0.00023	0.00019
0.23 (Sol C)	0.042	0.042	0.045	0.0027	0.00032	0.00025

TABLE II.

Concentration of the sol containing 0.23 gm. of TiO_2 in 100 c.c. of the sol.

P. c. of methyl alcohol.	Equicoagulating concentrations in normality :				
	KCl	KNO_3	K_2SO_4	$\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$
0	0.0167	0.0176	0.0019	0.00023	0.00019
2.5	0.0154	0.0176	0.00174	0.00022	0.00019
5	0.0147	0.0176	0.00166	0.00022	0.00019
10	0.0141	0.0176	0.00158	0.0002	0.00019
25	0.0131	0.0176	0.00143	0.000178	0.00021

TABLE III.

P. c. of ethyl alcohol.	Sol B.				
	KCl	Equicoagulating concentration in normality.			
		KNO ₃	K ₂ SO ₄	K ₃ Fe (CN) ₆	K ₄ Fe (CN) ₆
0	·0166	·0172	·0019	·00023	·000192
2·5	·0161	·0172	·0017	·0002	·000179
5	·0172	·0172	·00162	·0002	·000179
10	·0172	·0172	·00143	·000192	·00017
25	·0142	·0147	·0013	·000172	·00016

Discussion.

Table I shows that less of an electrolyte is necessary for coagulation, when the concentration of hydrosol is diminished. It is well-known that other hydroxide sols on dilution require smaller concentrations of electrolytes for coagulation. It is not possible however to enter into further discussions on the observed difference between the coagulation values of sols A and B in the absence of the measurement of the charge and the size of the particles. The coagulating capacities of the different anions are in the order: Ferri > Ferro > Sulphate > Chloride > Nitrate > Bromide, in conformity to the valency rule, and titanium hydroxide sol behaves as a typical positively charged hydrosol in this respect. The marked difference between the coagulating concentrations of all the electrolytes for sols B and C shows that, with time, changes take place in the sol which result in an increased stability. The nature of these changes requires further investigation. It may be remarked that the relative order of the coagulating concentrations of the different anions remains unchanged.

Tables II and III show that the hydrosol is sensitised by methyl and ethyl alcohols. The sensitising effect depends on the nature of the electrolyte. It will be noticed, however, that the coagulating concentration of potassium nitrate remains entirely unaffected in presence of even 25% methyl alcohol, whereas in the case of ethyl alcohol, it remains unaffected, up to 10%. But 25% of ethyl alcohol sensitises the sol towards potassium nitrate. Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 349) have observed similar

behaviour with acids. Against potassium ferrocyanide, the sol is stabilised at higher percentages of methyl alcohol, whereas it is always sensitised in presence of ethyl alcohol. No satisfactory explanation of these observations is possible, and various reasons have been assigned to account for the effect of non-electrolytes by different authors that the effect of the non-electrolyte is specific and depends on its nature, as also on that of the electrolyte and the sol: the change in the coagulating concentration of the electrolyte is generally not very large. It is possible that the addition of a non-electrolyte produces mutually opposing effects as has been suggested by the above authors, so that the limits of variation in the coagulating concentration become small and in some cases the opposing effects neutralise each other. It is also possible that the explanation of coagulation is to be sought in a property of the electrolyte which is mainly determined by its nature and stoichiometric concentration (Mukherjee, Rai-Chaudhury and Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 735), and that other factors such as activity of the ions and the dielectric constant and the changes in surface tension play a less important role.

Summary.

Titanium oxide hydrosol behaves as a typical positively charged hydrosol. The coagulating capacity of potassium salts is in the order: Ferri > Ferro > Sulphate > Chloride > Nitrate > Bromide and has been observed to remain unaffected by the quality or age for the samples used. The sol is sensitised in presence of methyl and ethyl alcohols towards the majority of electrolytes studied. On 'ageing' the sol becomes remarkably stable against coagulation by electrolyte.

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